

Lessons for AI Governance from Atoms for Peace

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In 1953, amid Cold War tensions and the looming threat of nuclear annihilation, U.S. President Dwight D. Eisenhower proposed a bold idea: harness the power of the atom for peace, not war. In his famous “Atoms for Peace” speech, Eisenhower proposed to prevent the spread of nuclear weapons by promoting peaceful applications of nuclear technology. This initiative laid the groundwork for the institutions, norms, and governance frameworks that continue to shape nuclear policy today.

Seven decades later, the world faces a new transformative technology—advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI). While AI differs from nuclear technology in many ways, its governance poses similarly high stakes. Rapidly advancing AI capabilities could lead to catastrophic outcomes¹, for example via misuse by malicious actors, accelerating arms races and the erosion of human control. Yet, with adequate safeguards in place, advanced AI could drive unprecedented scientific advancements and economic prosperity. Recognizing this, analysts frequently draw on nuclear governance as a model for AI governance, with some proposals^{2,3} explicitly drawing on Eisenhower’s framework.

In this two-part series, we take a closer look at “Atoms for Peace” in order to help readers better assess proposals for AI which invoke elements of this framework. Part 1 explores how Atoms for Peace shaped nuclear governance, detailing its logic, successes, and shortcomings. Part 2 identifies key challenges in adapting this framework to advanced AI and suggests a broader approach to AI nonproliferation. We provide a summary of key takeaways below.

Summary

Eisenhower's initiative sought to prevent nuclear Armageddon through a grand bargain: nations would accept international oversight and limitations on weapons development in exchange for access to peaceful nuclear technology and expertise. The U.S. used its significant lead in nuclear technology to make binding commitments toward peaceful use and risk reduction. Simultaneously, Atoms for Peace served as a Cold War strategy, reinforcing U.S. technological leadership while containing Soviet influence. This approach contributed to the creation of

¹ Hendrycks, D., Mazeika, M., & Woodside, T. (2023). *An Overview of Catastrophic AI Risks* (No. arXiv:2306.12001). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2306.12001>

² Roberts, P. S. (2019). *AI for Peace. War on the Rocks*. <http://warontherocks.com/2019/12/ai-for-peace/>

³ O’Keefe, C. (2024). *Chips for Peace: How the U.S. and Its Allies Can Lead on Safe and Beneficial AI*. Lawfare. <https://www.lawfaremedia.org/article/chips-for-peace--how-the-u.s.-and-its-allies-can-lead-on-safe-and-beneficial-ai>

institutions such as the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and helped shape international norms around nuclear cooperation. However, it also had unintended consequences, including the acceleration of nuclear proliferation in some cases and the entrenchment of Cold War divisions.

Several challenges complicate the endeavor of adapting the logic of Atoms for Peace to AI governance. First, establishing a 'grand bargain' – trading access to benefits for restrictions on dangerous uses – is challenging because AI lacks an obvious "weapons-grade" equivalent, and reliably verifying the safety of advanced AI is currently very difficult. Second, intense global competition creates powerful incentives to prioritize rapid development, making it hard for leading nations or developers to credibly commit to prioritizing safety or leverage a technological lead for risk reduction. Finally, attempting to control AI proliferation by restricting access to essential hardware like advanced chips risks repeating Cold War dynamics; such measures could deepen geopolitical divides, potentially provoke an AI arms race, and increase global instability.

We suggest AI governance could benefit from a broader concept of nonproliferation. This concept would move beyond hardware restrictions to focus on preventing dangerous AI capabilities. We examine "if-then commitments" as one example of a capability-focused approach. This approach could help address some identified challenges. The bargain in if-then commitments involves allowing continued AI development unless pre-agreed "capability triggers" are flagged during evaluations. This relies on defining thresholds for potentially dangerous AI capabilities, could enhance the credibility of safety commitments, and may create space for inclusive global cooperation on shared safety standards.

Part 1: Atoms for Peace

Logic and Strategy

In the early 1950s, the United States and Soviet Union were locked in a nuclear arms race, each developing ever more destructive weapons. President Eisenhower, seeking to ease global fears and reframe the nuclear narrative, unveiled the "Atoms for Peace" proposal in a speech to the UN General Assembly on December 8, 1953. In this address, Eisenhower acknowledged the grave risks of nuclear war but stated an American commitment to "*find the way by which the miraculous inventiveness of man shall not be dedicated to his death, but consecrated to his life.*"⁴

At its core, Atoms for Peace proposed an international exchange: countries would forgo nuclear weapons development in return for access to peaceful nuclear technology under international oversight. This arrangement created the foundation for the eventual Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT), which took effect in 1970.⁵ The bargain involved

⁴ [Atoms for Peace Speech | IAEA](#)

⁵ [Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons \(NPT\) – UNODA](#)

nuclear powers contributing fissile material to an international "bank" supervised by the United Nations, with this material dedicated exclusively to peaceful applications in energy, medicine, and agriculture. Non-nuclear states would receive technological benefits while agreeing not to develop weapons, and nuclear-armed nations committed to gradual disarmament efforts. This framework attempted to balance two competing interests: preventing the spread of nuclear weapons while ensuring all nations could benefit from nuclear science's peaceful applications. The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) emerged as the primary oversight body for this arrangement.

The United States leveraged its advanced position in nuclear technology to establish credibility and leadership in peaceful nuclear cooperation. This approach included passage of the Atomic Energy Act of 1954⁶, which created the legal basis for international nuclear cooperation, distribution of research reactors, specialized training, and nuclear fuel to allies and neutral countries, and establishment of the IAEA in 1957⁷ as an institutional embodiment of Eisenhower's vision. The United States also created verification mechanisms to ensure nuclear assistance wasn't diverted to military programs. By sharing nuclear expertise under controlled conditions, the United States positioned itself as the principal architect of the international nuclear order. This technical leadership reinforced American influence in shaping global nuclear norms and practices.

Beyond its stated humanitarian aims, Atoms for Peace functioned as a sophisticated Cold War strategy with multiple objectives. It presented American technological prowess in a benevolent light to counter Soviet influence and won support in developing nations by offering advanced technology and energy solutions. The initiative reassured European allies about America's commitment to peace while simultaneously encouraging their participation in NATO's nuclear deterrence strategy. It maintained strategic advantage by controlling which nuclear technologies were shared and with whom, and created a narrative of American leadership in peaceful development that contrasted with perceptions of Soviet militarism. President Eisenhower's initiative reflected his dual ambitions: to be recognized as a peacemaker while effectively containing communism's spread.⁸ The program's humanitarian framing masked its function as an instrument of geopolitical competition, allowing the United States to shape Cold War dynamics while appearing generous rather than aggressive.

Successes of Atoms for Peace

The Atoms for Peace program left a mixed legacy, but it achieved several notable successes that reshaped global nuclear affairs. Institution-building was perhaps its most enduring accomplishment. Eisenhower's initiative directly led to the creation of the IAEA in 1957, introducing the concept of international nuclear inspections and safeguards. For the first time,

⁶ [Atomic Energy Act of 1954](#)

⁷ [The Statute of the IAEA | IAEA](#)

⁸ Chernus, I. (Ed.). (2002). *Eisenhower's Atoms for Peace* (1st ed). Texas A & M University Press.

an international body was empowered to monitor nuclear facilities to ensure material wasn't diverted to bombs.

Atoms for Peace also fundamentally changed global attitudes toward nuclear energy. Eisenhower's optimistic framing helped normalize the idea that nuclear technology could be a tool not just of war, but of progress and human well-being. In the decades following the speech, dozens of countries launched nuclear research and power programs with U.S. or international assistance. By the 1960s and 1970s, reactors provided electricity in nations from France to India, and isotopes improved medical treatments and agricultural techniques worldwide. A recent speech delivered by World Nuclear Association Director General Sama Bilbao y León to the Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars noted that Eisenhower's "*one seed*" of an idea grew into a "*forest of possibilities*" in peaceful nuclear applications—from 400+ reactors supplying clean power to advances in cancer radiotherapy.⁹ While one can debate how much credit is due to Atoms for Peace versus other factors, the program undeniably accelerated the diffusion of scientific knowledge and nuclear infrastructure for civilian purposes. It made nuclear energy cooperation immensely popular and gave momentum to international scientific collaboration at a time of East–West polarization.

Crucially, Atoms for Peace established the normative groundwork for what became the global nonproliferation regime. As historian Peter Lavoy observes¹⁰, the initiative produced many key elements we now take for granted: "*the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), the concept of nuclear safeguards, and most importantly, the norm of nuclear nonproliferation*" as an expected behavior of responsible states. Before Eisenhower's proposal, there was little international consensus on how to reconcile peaceful nuclear pursuits with the prevention of weapons spread. Afterward, however imperfectly, a norm emerged that countries could access nuclear technology conditionally – i.e. if they committed not to build nuclear weapons and accepted inspections. A major consequence of the proposal was also the very idea of an eventual total nuclear disarmament. These elements were later codified in the NPT (1968), but its philosophical underpinnings trace back to Atoms for Peace. In short, Eisenhower's gambit demonstrated the value of combining carrots and sticks: offering technological benefits and international legitimacy as incentives for arms restraint. That approach has remained central to nuclear governance and offers a potentially useful template for AI governance.

Shortcomings and Unintended Consequences

For all its idealism, Atoms for Peace had serious shortcomings that tempered its legacy. Nuclear proliferation did not halt—in some cases, it arguably accelerated under the cover of peaceful aid. As some analysts¹¹ have noted, "*it is legitimate to ask whether Atoms for Peace accelerated*

⁹ *Viewpoint: The legacy of Eisenhower's Atoms for Peace speech.* (2023). World Nuclear News. <https://world-nuclear-news.org/articles/viewpoint-the-legacy-of-eisenhower-s-atoms-for-peace>

¹⁰ Lavoy, Peter R. 2003. "The Enduring Effects of Atoms for Peace." *Arms Control Today*, December 2003. <https://www.armscontrol.org/act/2003-12/features/enduring-effects-atoms-peace>.

¹¹ Weiss, L. (2003). Atoms for Peace. *Bulletin of the Atomic Scientists*, 59(6), 34–44. <https://doi.org/10.2968/059006009>

proliferation by helping some nations achieve more advanced arsenals than would have otherwise been the case. The jury has been in for some time on this question, and the answer is yes." The program hastened the global diffusion of nuclear know-how, and some recipient nations – notably India, Pakistan, and Israel – diverted ostensibly peaceful assistance into their weapons development efforts. For example, India's first nuclear explosive in 1974 was enabled by a Canadian-supplied reactor and U.S.-supplied heavy water from cooperative agreements in the 1950s. Similarly, research reactors and training provided under Atoms for Peace helped jump-start programs that later produced weapons in Israel and Pakistan. The hope had been that introducing international oversight would counteract the risks of sharing nuclear technology, but in the first decade, safeguards were weak or nonexistent. This enforcement gap meant countries could receive nuclear hardware and expertise while remaining outside any binding nonproliferation agreement until the NPT regime took hold years later.

Another shortcoming was the program's geopolitical imbalance and resulting mistrust. In practice, Atoms for Peace became a largely U.S.-led, Western-centric enterprise. The Soviet Union, distrustful of American intentions, refused to pool any of its fissile material and dismissed Eisenhower's plan as propaganda. Non-aligned nations in the Global South were also cautious: while many welcomed nuclear assistance, they resented the implicit bargain that demanded renouncing weapons options in exchange. Countries like India, which saw nuclear technology as a ticket to modernity and international stature, bristled at the notion of technology control by the great powers. The result was a trust deficit: some states felt the rules of the emerging nuclear order were being written *for* them rather than *with* them. This partisan dynamic undermined the spirit of cooperation that Eisenhower's rhetoric espoused.

Critics also argue that Eisenhower's emphasis on the "peaceful atom" carried a paradoxical message: it framed nuclear technology as the harbinger of peace and progress, yet implicitly accepted the permanence of superpower nuclear arsenals as the guarantor of world stability. In other words, Atoms for Peace did not directly pursue disarmament; it was a peace through strength and technology management, not a peace through eliminating the Bomb. This approach, which historian Ira Chernus terms "*apocalypse management*,"¹² normalized the indefinite existence of nuclear weapons as a backdrop for peace. One could argue it sidestepped the deeper ethical question of the arms race and instead focused on managing its side-effects.

Lastly, enforcement and safeguards under Atoms for Peace were initially too lax to prevent determined proliferators from cheating. The IAEA eventually developed robust inspection practices, but in the late 1950s and 1960s, the regime lacked teeth – there were no mandatory inspections until states began joining the NPT. Israel received a research reactor from France and simply kept it outside of safeguards, using it to produce plutonium for weapons. Pakistan received extensive training of nuclear scientists through Western programs well before any oversight regime existed. The technology outpaced the governance in those early years, a cautionary tale for any similar framework in AI or other domains. It was only after proliferation

¹² Chernus, I. (Ed.). (2002). *Eisenhower's Atoms for Peace* (1st ed). Texas A & M University Press.

cases came to light that the world tightened nuclear rules (for instance, India's 1974 test led to the Nuclear Suppliers Group's formation to better control exports). The Atoms for Peace era thus teaches that a voluntary, trust-based system can be exploited if not backed by verification and consequences. Balancing openness and security is incredibly challenging: too much openness can aid malign actors, while too much restriction stifles beneficial innovation. Eisenhower's program attempted to walk that line, with mixed results.

Part 2: Chips for Peace?

The need to develop strategy and governance for advanced AI has become urgent, particularly as the catastrophic scale of risks from increasingly advanced AI models become clear, and as destabilizing competitive dynamics emerge. The parallels to nuclear technology and Cold War dynamics are perhaps more apparent now than then ever. But does the logic and strategy of 'Atoms for Peace' apply? Our analysis reveals three key challenges.

1. Finding a Grand Bargain for Advanced AI

Although AI is a dual-use technology, identifying a grand bargain is tricky.

In comparison to nuclear weapons, AI's risks are diverse and diffuse, ranging from smaller and more immediate risks such as algorithmic bias, privacy erosion, and job displacement to broader societal-scale concerns such as robust totalitarianism and loss of human control. Reaching international consensus on which AI risks are the most urgent to mitigate is difficult.

Further, while there is a relatively clear distinction between military and civilian applications of nuclear technology, it is difficult to distinguish between dangerous and beneficial AI. Frontier AI models –general-purpose AI models at the forefront of AI capabilities– offer the closest analogy for nuclear technology as these models could have dangerous capabilities sufficient to pose catastrophic risks.¹³ Yet, assessing whether AI model capabilities are approaching critical thresholds is much more complicated than determining whether a country's nuclear activities are weapons-related or civilian. Dangerous AI capabilities can emerge unexpectedly, often in ways even developers struggle to anticipate or detect. And, unlike nuclear technology, there is no universally recognized "weapons-grade" AI model.

For these reasons, current efforts to identify catastrophically-risk AI models often rely on proxies such as chips, compute or semiconductor supply chains, not necessarily because these are great proxies, but because precise thresholds for catastrophically dangerous AI capabilities are difficult to define.

¹³ Anderljung, M., Barnhart, J., Korinek, A., Leung, J., O'Keefe, C., Whittlestone, J., Avin, S., Brundage, M., Bullock, J., Cass-Beggs, D., Chang, B., Collins, T., Fist, T., Hadfield, G., Hayes, A., Ho, L., Hooker, S., Horvitz, E., Kolt, N., Schuett, J., Shavit, Y., Siddarth, D., Trager, R., and Wolf, K. (2023). Frontier AI Regulation: Managing Emerging Risks to Public Safety. ArXiv preprint arXiv:2307.03718v4.

Identifying “peaceful” uses of AI is equally challenging. Characteristics such as the opacity of AI models, their context-dependent risks, and their vulnerability to manipulation, make it difficult to verify the safety of AI systems. This makes it fundamentally difficult to leverage sharing the tremendous benefits of AI as an incentive.

What would an AI grand bargain actually entail? Under Atoms for Peace, the exchange was clear: access to peaceful nuclear technology in return for international oversight and restrictions on weapons development. In the AI context, a comparable bargain would need to offer meaningful benefits (e.g., access to safe advanced AI models and resources) in exchange for verifiable safety commitments and oversight of high-risk applications. However, the technical challenges outlined above make this difficult to operationalize. Much research and policy work is needed—particularly in areas such as Frontier AI capability evaluations, safety standards and risk assessment—to define the core components of a grand bargain.

2. Leveraging Technological Leads

Atoms for Peace leveraged America's nuclear lead to make credible commitments toward peaceful use. Assuming a coalition of the U.S. and its allies can sustain an advantage in Frontier AI and semiconductor supply chains, can this lead be used to commit to AI risk reduction?

Several commitment problems complicate this endeavor. First, the lead must be substantial enough to give a ‘coalition of the [cautious](#)’ sufficient time to make meaningful progress on AI safety. However, recent developments—such as rapid scaling, model distillation and the immanence of AI agents—create uncertainty about both how long the U.S. and its allies can maintain an advantage and how long it will take to develop the necessary technical and governance solutions. Second, the coalition must credibly commit to moving cautiously on Frontier AI development—a challenge made particularly difficult by intensifying U.S.-China competition for AI dominance, which incentivizes a ‘race to the bottom’ in safety. Finally, the coalition must ensure that its risk-reduction efforts do not inadvertently accelerate the development of dangerous AI capabilities. Safety research itself can contribute to capability gains—historically several fields of AI safety research, such as interpretability and preference learning, have driven developments leading to more powerful AI models and this is likely to continue in the future.

These commitment problems reveal important differences from the nuclear precedent. When the U.S. leveraged its nuclear lead through Atoms for Peace, it did so from a position of overwhelming technological advantage that would persist for years. In contrast, the AI landscape is unpredictable, with leadership positions potentially shifting in months rather than decades. Additionally, while nuclear technology development requires massive state-backed infrastructure, AI development is more distributed and often led by private companies with their own competitive incentives.

Addressing these commitment problems will require not only policy levers, but also technical mechanisms that enable verifiable commitments to cautious AI development.

3. Strategic competition

Finally, we need to consider what a ‘Cold War strategy’ would look like in the context of AI. The Cold War emerged post-WWII, featuring stark ideological blocs and existential nuclear fears – a context arguably different from today’s more complex geopolitical landscape, fluid alliances, and the specific nature of US-China competition.

Nonetheless, some current strategies echo past containment efforts. Coordinated export controls on high-performance AI chips and manufacturing equipment, for instance, aim to slow AI progress in rival states and consolidate a technological lead for a U.S.-led coalition. While the context differs, the *logic* mirrors Cold War-era technology containment strategies, where the West restricted access to sensitive military and dual-use technologies to prevent Soviet advancements.

The lesson from Atoms for Peace is cautionary: while it helped establish a U.S.-led nuclear order, it also reinforced Cold War divisions, pushing adversaries toward independent weapons programs and fueling decades of arms racing. Similarly, strict AI export controls could drive states outside the coalition toward self-sufficiency in AI infrastructure. This could result in a bifurcated AI ecosystem with incompatible AI safety standards and lower prospects for broad international coordination.

More dangerously, export controls could reinforce the perception that AI leadership is a zero-sum game, causing restricted states to shift their focus toward AI military applications, and perhaps leading to an AI-arms race. In this scenario, with rival states racing to deploy AI-enhanced capabilities before their adversaries, integrating not-fully-safe advanced AI into military functions ranging from autonomous weapons to strategic decision-support, the result could be greater unpredictability in strategic decision-making, heightened crisis instability and an increased risk of unintended conflict escalation.

Conclusion

The AI-nuclear analogy is valuable not because the technologies are highly similar, but because examining historical precedents can help structure our thinking about the governance of powerful dual-use technologies. Our analysis of Atoms for Peace reveals that applying a similar logic and strategy to advanced AI would face significant challenges.

A more effective strategy could take inspiration not just from Atoms for Peace but from the broader concept of nonproliferation. While nuclear nonproliferation serves a specific function in the context of Atoms for Peace, it has since become a broader international norm and approach to mitigating catastrophic risks from dangerous technologies.

Applying this broader concept, AI nonproliferation would not be narrowly defined as controlling model weights or restricting access to high-performance chips, since these alone do not determine AI’s risk profile. Instead, a broader notion of AI nonproliferation would focus on controlling dangerous AI capabilities—particularly those that disproportionately carry

societal-scale or catastrophic risks. As the science of AI capability evaluations improve, and governments become better equipped with empirical evidence, we could move away from relying on proxies.

Further, AI nonproliferation could focus not only on preventing the spread of Frontier AI to actors without adequate safeguards (horizontal proliferation) but also on curbing the unchecked escalation of AI capabilities (vertical proliferation). Atoms for Peace primarily focused on horizontal proliferation, and this focus is maintained in some analogous proposals for AI.¹⁴ Yet, vertical AI proliferation is equally destabilizing—if one actor pushes too far and too fast, AI capabilities could exceed our ability to control them before safety mechanisms are fully developed.

[If-then commitments](#)¹⁵ exemplify an approach focused on preventing the vertical proliferation of dangerous AI capabilities. The general idea is that AI developers commit to pause, delay, or limit development and deployment when specific "trip-wire capabilities" are detected through ongoing evaluations. This approach provides some mechanisms to address each of the three key challenges we've identified.

First, if-then commitments do not require broader international agreement on which risks should be prioritized or what the weapons-grade equivalent of advanced AI is *ex ante*. Instead, AI developers agree that certain situations would require risk mitigation *if* they came to pass. In avoiding *unnecessary* restrictions on innovation, if-then commitments support the development of "peaceful" AI. In other words, the grand bargain is that developers maintain freedom to innovate and advance AI capabilities, while accepting pre-defined limits when specific risk thresholds are reached. This also makes a grand bargain more technically feasible and more politically palatable, as it grounds governance in empirical evidence rather than speculative risks.

Second, if-then commitments address some specific commitment problems. For example, by pre-defining specific "trip-wire capabilities" and conditionally committing to risk mitigation, they add credibility to commitments to develop responsibly. Further, if-then commitments could mitigate the "racing" dynamic that otherwise incentivizes cutting corners on safety. If all leading developers were to publicly commit to the same capability triggers, the competitive advantage of rushing ahead diminishes, as reaching certain capability thresholds would activate the pre-committed limitations regardless of who gets there first.

Third, they may help avoid a bifurcated AI ecosystem by creating governance frameworks that can function across geopolitical divides. Unlike export controls focused on hardware, capability-based commitments can be adopted by any developer regardless of nationality, potentially enabling inclusive cooperation around shared safety standards. Constructive

¹⁴ For example, see "Nonproliferation" in [Chips for Peace](#) and [Superintelligence Strategy](#).

¹⁵ Karnofsky, H. (2024). If-then Commitments for AI Risk Reduction. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/09/if-then-commitments-for-ai-risk-reduction?lang=en>

relationships could be established with Global South nations based on a shared commitment towards open tech transfers and ensuring a safe and flourishing future with advanced AI. This is necessary in order to avoid repeating the mistakes of the Atoms for Peace, where badly framed measures and inconsistent application of rules caused a loss of trust and led to countries seeking other partners.

While if-then commitments currently exist in some form in responsible scaling policies and other policies voluntarily put forth by leading AI companies, these could eventually be enforced by an international regime, much the way the IAEA and NPT institutionalized nuclear nonproliferation following Atoms for Peace. Eventually, this could lead to agreements on restrictions and safety measures for dangerous AI use cases, including lethal autonomous weapon systems and nuclear weapon command and control.

If-then commitments illustrate that we don't necessarily need universal agreement on AI risks or for cautious developers to maintain an undisputed lead in order to slow the proliferation of dangerous AI capabilities. However, for AI nonproliferation to work, we do need a robust science of capability evaluation that can reliably detect when AI models approach dangerous thresholds, as well as robust verification mechanisms. Just as voluntary oversight proved insufficient in nuclear governance, AI governance initiatives must incorporate mandatory, transparent evaluations and credible enforcement from the outset. By carefully balancing openness and security, proactively addressing geopolitical mistrust, and designing adaptive institutions, AI governance can avoid repeating historical mistakes. Ultimately, effective AI nonproliferation will depend on clear capability thresholds, rigorous verification, and inclusive international cooperation—all of them areas where AI governance can learn from nuclear governance.